

THE DEVELOPMENT OF BRITISH CHILDREN'S LITERATURE

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Annotation

This article explores British children's literature has its particular historic status and social value. From the Industrial Revolution to Children's Literature Revolution: A Study on Modern and Contemporary British Fairy-tale Stories illustrates the main thread of the artistic components and evolutionary trend in the history of British children's literature. It enriches the content and broadens the horizons of foreign literature studies in Uzbekistan. British children's literature has a rich and ever-evolving history, offering a fascinating journey through changing times and evolving ideas about childhood, education, and storytelling.

Keywords: children's literature, fairytale, imagery, fantasy genre, literary study, symbols

Аннотация

В этой статье исследуется британская детская литература с ее особым историческим статусом и социальной ценностью. Книга «От промышленной революции к революции в детской литературе: A Study on Modern and Contemporary British Fairy-tale Stories» иллюстрирует основную нить художественных компонентов и эволюционных тенденций в истории британской детской литературы. Это обогащает содержание и расширяет горизонты зарубежного литературоведения в Узбекистане. Британская детская литература имеет богатую и постоянно развивающуюся историю, предлагая увлекательное путешествие через меняющиеся времена и эволюционирующие идеи о детстве, образовании и повествовании.

Ключевые слова: детская литература, сказка, образность, жанр фэнтези, литературоведение, символы.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada ingliz bolalar adabiyoti o'zining alohida tarixiy maqomi va ijtimoiy qiymati bilan ko'rib chiqiladi. Sanoat inqilobidan bolalar adabiyotidagi inqilobgacha: zamonaviy Britaniya ertak hikoyalari bo'yicha tadqiqot Britaniya bolalar adabiyoti tarixidagi badiiy komponentlar va evolyutsion tendentsiyalarning asosiy yo'nalishini ko'rsatadi. Bu O'zbekistondagi xorijiy adabiyotshunoslik fanining mazmunini boyitib, dunyoqarashini kengaytiradi. Britaniya bolalar adabiyoti boy va doimiy

rivojlanib boruvchi tarixga ega bo'lib, o'zgarib borayotgan zamonlar va bolalik, ta'lim va hikoyalar haqidagi g'oyalarni o'zgartirish orqali qiziqarli ma'lumotlarni taklif etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: bolalar adabiyoti, ertak, tasvir, fantaziya janri, adabiyotshunoslik, ramzlar.

Children's literature of a nation reflects its thinking mode and spirit. British children's literature not only invigorates British literature but also helps with the formation and development of the indigenous literature and culture in Britain. Therefore, British children's literature has its particular historic status and social value. From the Industrial Revolution to Children's Literature Revolution: A Study on Modern and Contemporary British Fairy-tale Stories illustrates the main thread of the artistic components and evolutionary trend in the history of British children's literature. It is the first book in China that focuses on the evolution of British fairy tales. Overcoming the narrow views on fairy-tale literature, it enriches the content and broadens the horizons of foreign literature studies in Uzbekistan. The book will certainly exert great influences on the macrocosmic studies on children's literature for its outstanding value in historic studies and its exemplary role in academic quality. British children's literature has a rich and ever-evolving history, offering a fascinating journey through changing times and evolving ideas about childhood, education, and storytelling. From moral instruction to fantastical adventures, the stories continue to inspire, educate, and entertain generations of readers.

The beginnings of early British Children's literature

The roots of British children's literature, though not as readily apparent as the flowering of the 19th century, lie in the 17th and 18th centuries, a period marked by social and intellectual upheaval. This nascent form of literature was characterized by a strong emphasis on moral instruction and religious education, yet within these didactic structures, seeds of imagination and storytelling began to take root.

The earliest forays into children's literature were often extensions of religious texts and devotional materials. John Bunyan's "Pilgrim's Progress" (1678), though intended for adults, served as a crucial touchstone. Its allegorical journey, filled with captivating characters and moral dilemmas, resonated with children, paving the way for accessible narratives with a spiritual undercurrent. Isaac Watts, an influential poet and hymn writer, further cemented this trend with his "Divine and Moral Songs for Children" (1715). The poems, imbued with religious themes and simple rhyme schemes, aimed to install Christian values in

young minds. While undeniably didactic, they also employed vivid imagery and engaging stories, hinting at the potential for storytelling to be more than just a tool for moral instruction. However, the shift towards a more child-centred approach began to emerge in the 18th century. Authors like Sarah Fielding, sister of the famous novelist Henry Fielding, penned works like "The Governess" (1749). This novel, while still grounded in moral lessons, aimed for a more engaging narrative style, introducing a young protagonist and a more relatable, everyday setting. The focus shifted from solely religious instruction to embracing the complexities of childhood experiences and social interactions.

The emergence of the "child reader" as a distinct audience was further propelled by the publication of "The History of Little Goody Two-Shoes" (1765), a fictionalized biography of a poor girl who through hard work and virtuous conduct, finds success and happiness. The story's simple language, relatable plot, and emphasis on the power of good deeds resonated with young readers, paving the way for more relatable narratives and less overtly didactic works.

The rise of the fairy tale as a genre also contributed to the development of British children's literature. Though initially rooted in oral traditions, collections like Charles Perrault's "Tales of Mother Goose" (1697) and the Brothers Grimm's "Children's and Household Tales" (1812), introduced magical elements, fantastical creatures, and compelling narratives that captured the imagination of children and adults alike. While these early works were often infused with religious and moral lessons, they also paved the way for a more nuanced understanding of childhood. They introduced engaging narratives, relatable characters, and imaginative elements that laid the foundation for the golden age of British children's literature that would flourish in the 19th century. These early works, though steeped in didacticism, ultimately helped shape the landscape for the development of a truly diverse and engaging world of children's literature.

Golden Age of Children's literature in Britain.

The Victorian era, spanning the mid-19th to early 20th centuries, witnessed a remarkable blossoming of British children's literature, often referred to as the "Golden Age." This period saw the emergence of iconic authors who revolutionized the genre, creating enduring classics that continue to captivate young readers today. The 19th century marked a turning point in recognizing children as a specific target audience. The burgeoning middle class, with its emphasis on education and leisure, created a demand for books tailored to young minds. This shift led to a surge in publications aimed at entertaining,

educating, and inspiring children. Whimsical Worlds and Timeless Themes: Authors like Lewis Carroll, with his "Alice's Adventures in Wonderland" (1865) and "Through the Looking-Glass" (1871), pushed the boundaries of imagination. His nonsensical stories, filled with talking animals, illogical situations, and witty wordplay, offered a refreshing departure from traditional children's literature. He challenged societal norms and embraced absurdity, sparking a fascination with the fantastical and the surreal. Charles Dickens, though primarily known for adult fiction, also penned enduring children's classics like "A Christmas Carol" (1843), which continues to resonate with its themes of compassion, redemption, and the importance of family. Dickens's vivid characters, relatable themes, and powerful social commentary, captivated readers young and old. Beatrix Potter, with her beloved "Peter Rabbit" series (1902), introduced a charming world of anthropomorphic animals and engaging narratives. Her stories were grounded in nature, promoting appreciation for the natural world and fostering a love for animals. Her simple language and charming illustrations made her stories accessible to young readers, while also teaching valuable lessons about responsibility, kindness, and the consequences of one's actions. Kenneth Grahame's "The Wind in the Willows" (1908) became a beloved classic, offering a charming and timeless tale of friendship, adventure, and the beauty of the English countryside. Grahame's whimsical characters and evocative descriptions of nature created a world that resonated with both children and adults. The Golden Age also witnessed a greater emphasis on emotional depth and psychological exploration in children's literature. Authors like A.A. Milne, with his "Winnie-the-Pooh" series (1926), presented characters who faced challenges and experienced a range of emotions, while maintaining a light-hearted and whimsical tone. Milne's stories offered comforting and relatable narratives about friendship, exploring the complexities of human relationships through the eyes of endearing characters. The Golden Age of British Children's literature produced a wealth of enduring classics that continue to inspire and entertain generations of readers. These stories, with their captivating narratives, whimsical characters, and timeless themes, have shaped the literary landscape, fostering a love for reading and imagination in countless young minds. The legacy of this period continues to influence contemporary children's literature, reminding us of the power of storytelling to engage, educate, and spark a lifelong passion for reading.

Modern Era of kid's literature in Great Britain

The modern era of British children's literature, spanning roughly from the mid-20th century to the present, is a vibrant tapestry of evolving themes, diverse voices, and innovative storytelling. It reflects a changing world, embracing multiculturalism, social issues, and new forms of media while retaining the core values of imagination and entertainment. Post-World War II literature saw a shift towards realism and a willingness to tackle complex themes. Authors like Roald Dahl, with his darkly humorous and often subversive stories, challenged societal norms and explored the complexities of family dynamics, loss, and coping with difficult emotions. His work, like "Matilda" (1988) and "Charlie and the Chocolate Factory" (1964), resonated with children facing similar challenges, offering a sense of empowerment and escape.

Writers like Jacqueline Wilson, known for her realistic and often poignant novels for young adults, delved into issues like family breakdown, peer pressure, and self-discovery. Her works like "The Story of Tracy Beaker" (1991) and "Double Act" (1996) gave voice to the experiences of children facing difficult circumstances, providing a sense of empathy and understanding. The modern era has seen a growing recognition of the importance of diversity and cultural representation in children's literature. Authors like Malorie Blackman, with her groundbreaking "Noughts & Crosses" series (2001), tackled themes of racism, prejudice, and social injustice, offering a powerful lens through which to explore complex social issues. Authors like S.K. Ali, with her award-winning "The Girl Who Drank the Moon" (2017), and Angie Thomas, with her poignant "The Hate U Give" (2017), continue to explore themes of race, identity, and social justice through compelling narratives, bringing diverse voices and experiences to the forefront of children's literature. Fantasy and Science Fiction: The legacy of classic fantasy and science fiction authors like C.S. Lewis and J.K. Rowling continues to inspire contemporary writers. Authors like Philip Pullman, with his "His Dark Materials" trilogy (1995-2000), and Suzanne Collins, with her "Hunger Games" trilogy (2008-2010), have created complex worlds and compelling narratives that explore themes of power, identity, and rebellion, captivating young readers with their imaginative storytelling.

The Future of British Children's Literature:

The modern era of British children's literature is marked by its adaptability, embracing diversity, tackling complex social issues, and exploring new forms of storytelling. It continues to evolve, reflecting the changing world and offering a platform for voices from all backgrounds. The future of British children's literature promises exciting possibilities, fueled by the creativity and

imagination of a new generation of authors, who are pushing boundaries and captivating readers with their powerful and engaging narratives.

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